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Embodied alien. Nobody - no body

Performance Paper

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Embodied alien. Nobody – no body

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Abstract. This paper presents a work in progress focusing on machinic feedback as a means of cyclic co-creation, in order to understand procedures of interaction, adaptation and expressivity in the context of technologically mediated performance. This is a part of a larger ongoing project focused on cross-adaptive modulations, AI, and their contribution towards the expansion of human actions on stage. AI methods, as automation and modulation in software, represent a disembodiment, acting both as an intimate and an alien partner in contexts where humans perform the physical action. Embodiment of the alien partner has its physical manifestation in an acoustic instrument (piano) equipped with transducers, and the resonances of the piano body thus become the common playground for the machine - human encounter.

Keywords: feedback, live interfaces, actuated instruments, machine learning, improvisation

Introduction

The use of microphones and loudspeakers as musical instruments has a rich history (Eck 2017), one that includes the use of electronic technology to control the feedback on acoustic musical instruments (Berdahl, Niemeyer, and Smith 2008), namely to pursue the idea of actuated musical instruments (Ângelo et al 2018). Within the project “Fostering innovation in musical performance research through the study and development of technologic interfaces”, we decided to base a number of experimental music approaches on the setup of an actuated grand piano. The basic setup was common to all approaches and was based on the digital control of the audio feedback happening between two transducers attached to the piano soundboard: a piezo transducer, acting as a contact microphone, and a contact loudspeaker (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Setup description

Together with the other members of the project — Øyvind Brandtsegg and Trond Engum (NTNU), Alfonso Benetti (INET-nd, UA) and Bruno Pereira (i2ADS, ESMAE) —, we developed and explored a few case studies around this setup, focusing on the use of feedback control techniques to allow for the introduction of digital signal processing of the

acoustic sound of the piano via the amplification attached to the soundboard. Thus, this paper focuses on machinic feedback as a means of cyclic co-creation that can underlie specific procedures of interaction, adaptation and expressivity in the context of technologically mediated performance.

Approach and implementation

The basic idea for this case study was to develop an algorithm capable of expressive control of the feedback loop, providing the means for a cyclic co-creation with the piano player. In order to achieve that, we devised a simple interface for the control of the feedback and trained a machine-learning model on data recorded during several performances played by a human player using the same interface.

The algorithm is based on the recording of the sound captured by the piezo transducer on a buffer, which is then made available for playback with spectral manipulation using five parameters:

- 1) Playback position, which defines a point in time for granular playback of the contents of the buffer.
- 2) Frequency of low-pass FFT crossover, which defines the highest FFT bin which is allowed to passthrough to the inverse FFT for playback.
- 3) Frequency of high-pass FFT crossover, which defines the lowest FFT bin which is allowed to passthrough to the inverse FFT for playback. If this is lower than the former, no audio will passthrough.
- 4) Minimum amplitude for FFT bin playback, which defines the minimum amplitude a given FFT bin must have to be allowed to passthrough to the inverse FFT for playback.
- 5) Time of automatic cross-fade between FFT frames, which defines how much time (and, consequently, how smooth) it takes for the change of parameters to be reflected of the playback of the subsequent FFT frames.

The implementation of this algorithm was made in Max/MSP, based on the techniques for spectral manipulation proposed by Jean-François Charles (2008). Albeit simple, this algorithm enables an easy and very expressive control of feedback by a human performer, which was what we aimed for in several rehearsals and public presentations. The adopted strategy for the musical gestures of this controlled feedback was always based on a simple set of principles:

- 1) Identify a suitable point (parameter 1) to start a new feedback gesture, based on a combination of both listening to the piano performance and looking at the sonogram of the recorded audio.
- 2) Select a value for parameters (5) based on the visual analysis of the complexity of the spectral content of the chosen playback point.
- 3) Manipulate parameters (1) to (4) based on reactions to the complete sonic performance.
- 4) Continue until the parameters reach a combination that generates no sonic output, point in which a new recording of the buffer starts, thus recording solely the acoustic output of the piano, until a new musical gesture starts.

All the data of these performances was recorded and used to train a combination of three machine-learning algorithms (MLAs), all having spectral frames as inputs:

- 1) MLA1 has as input the spectral content of the frames currently being recorded and is responsible for identifying suitable frames to start feedback gestures. It thus provides a Boolean decision based on the analysis of the spectral input. Since the recording is only active when no audio is being output by the system, MLA1 is only active during acoustic piano solos.
- 2) MLA2 has as input the single spectral frame selected by MLA1 and as output a single value for parameter 5.
- 3) MLA3 has the most complex task, which is to output values for parameters (1) to (4) based on the spectral content of each frame of the audio input. MLA3 is only active when there is audio playback by the system, hence it always "listens" to the combination of the acoustic piano as played by the player and the system output as amplified by the contact loudspeaker, both captured by the piezo transducer. Even though the decisions of MLA3 are made for each spectral frame, a smoothness of the audio output depends mostly on the value of parameter (5) as selected by MLA2.

A simple envelope follower tracks the system output, looking for silent moments in which to retrigger the audio recording of the acoustic piano to restart a new musical gesture. A second envelope follower tracks the audio input, disabling the output of MLA1 when the audio input is silent. This way, the computer will never start a new gesture when the pianist is silent, which is then used to control both the beginning and the end of the performance.

Performance implications

For a performer of an acoustical instrument such as the piano, relating to electronic contents – be it in live electronic or pre-recorded contexts – involves specific challenges: the corporality of the electronic sounds function as an alien sound when compared with the acoustic properties and affordances of musical instruments, and their historic / symbolic background bears on performance both in technical and gestural terms. Moreover, as Simon Waters states, when proposing an ethics of listening in the context of improvisation, “the objects with which we surround ourselves (such as musical instruments) act as prosthetic sensors, amplifiers, and transducers of our interactions with our environment and with others, [...] a capacity for empathy can be imaginatively designed into the non-human agents with which we interact” (Waters 2018, 1). He also adds that, “in a network of human and non-human actors, empathy might be ‘designed for’ – by looking at attributions of indigenous agency to circuits, computers, and software; to knobs and physical interfaces; and to sound itself” (Waters 2018, 3). Visually (especially for an audience) and aurally (in particular for the performer), the use of interfaces require a particular mode of listening, which informs and shapes the manners in which acoustically-produced materials are intertwined with electronic contents.

In 2000, Simon Emmerson, when evaluating extant tendencies in music produced by and through technology, identified two main streams: one that persists on “representing humanity” (Emmerson 2000, 212), another that conveys a “clear imprint of the human *will* rather than the human *presence*” (idem, 213). In a more recent publication, however, Emmerson (2018) acknowledges a broader and polystylistic taxonomy of forms at the core of live interfaces, demonstrating the wide range afforded by current developments. This wide range implies adaptive modes of listening and playing, reflected in the current project.

Some specific issues were identified during studio work, undertaken in Norway and Portugal from October to January 2020:

- contrarily to the voice, for instance, which displays a wide inherent adaptability in timbre, acoustical instruments, especially the piano, are often bound to fixed height and timbre features. The piano, with its wide range of frequencies and volume, can become overbearing, and this fact imposes several constraints when working with feedback, requiring constant adaptation, and the choice of specific and effective strategies;
- feedback mimics and extends piano sounds but, from the pianist’s point of view, the connection can range from a recognizable identification of standard piano features to a totally alien content. At this far end of the scope, the issue of selecting improvised contents becomes more critical (i.e., assuming a non-tonal, non-jazz approach);
- extended techniques can successfully bridge that divide. Their “improper” (Vaes 2009) sound quality, and the implicit deterritorialization of the piano sound, can act as “proper” affordances when combined with digitally generated sounds. Thus, extended techniques can function as a mediator, levelling the transition from electronic to acoustical, and vice-versa;
- we can therefore label the performative results as a controlled improvisation, focusing on creating a sound scape, and engaging with the effects created and generated rather than adopting a virtuosistic discourse and techniques.

In conclusion, AI methods, as automation and modulation in software, represent a disembodiment, acting both as an intimate and an alien partner in contexts where humans perform the physical action. The embodiment of the alien partner displays its physical manifestation in the acoustic instrument equipped with transducers, and the resonances of the piano body thus become the common playground for the machine - human encounter.

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